

A Study of RISC and CISC Processors

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Abstract—This paper explores the study of the two significant developments in processor technology, namely the RISC (Reduced Instruction Set Computer) and the CISC (Complex Instruction Set Computer). RISC vs CISC was always a heated topic in the 1980s and 90s when the computer world faced problems like memory space and execution time complexities. These constraints led to the existence of these instruction sets and were a revolution in the processor world. Results in the paper are discussed in terms of principal features, the advantages and disadvantages of both RISC and CISC processors. Based on these attributes, the preferable architecture model is determined to be RISC.

Index Terms—micro-programming, processors, memory, hardware, architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

Around 1984, IBM and DEC accepted micro-programming for their computer systems, and CISC's instruction set architectures like VAX and Intel 80x86 came into use where engineers came across the issue of enabling large numbers of ISA and microcode interpreters. So, the only two possible solutions seemed to be either having a less complex ISA or changing the control store memory into cache, which enables modification of memory content according to the requirement rather than holding a different ISA interpreter every single time to fit the changes in the contents of instruction memory. Through the approach mentioned in the latter half, it was observed that the pipelining technique was possible which led to fewer clock cycles. This style of ISA came to be known as RISC. Even though RISC faced performance issues with more instructions than CISC, it still qualified as the most benign choice among the instruction set architectures as described by D.Patterson through the following formula. [2]

$$\frac{\text{Instructions}}{\text{program}} \times \frac{\text{Clock Cycle}}{\text{Instructions}} \times \frac{\text{Time}}{\text{Clock Cycle}} = \frac{\text{Time}}{\text{Program}}$$

As observed from the above formula, even though CISC processors had fewer instructions to implement per program execution, the fewer clock cycles per instruction on average by RISC processors took the advantage.

Irrespective of the RISC vs CISC issue, both the processors enjoyed a good share of popularity in the computing landscape. But recently, the ARM ISA (Advanced RISC Machine) and the x86 ISA (a CISC ISA) have influenced the computing domains ranging from desktops, servers to mobile and low-power embedded systems. [1] However, as the processors

evolved, newer microprocessors like the Intel 80x86, with limited addressing modes and way fewer instructions, turned out to be more enhanced processors than the others. [3] In recent decades, the RISC vs. CISC debate has evolved. Today, RISC architectures, such as ARM, are widely used in mobile devices, embedded systems, and even desktops, exemplified by Apple's transition to ARM-based M1 chips. On the other hand, CISC architectures like Intel's x86 continue to dominate in high-performance servers and PCs. Despite the initial advantages of one over the other, modern processors increasingly blur the lines between RISC and CISC.[7] This paper compares RISC and CISC architectures, focusing on key features, advantages, and disadvantages, with particular emphasis on their application in modern computing. Based on these factors, we explore the argument that RISC may be the more advantageous architecture in many contexts today.

II. OVERVIEW OF RISC (REDUCED INSTRUCTION SET COMPUTER)

A RISC is referred to as processor architecture that is designed to perform operations through simpler and a smaller number of instructions. The first RISC processor - RISC I was designed in 1982 and RISC II in 1984.[4] Below described are some of the features and characteristics of RISC:

A. Pipelining

Pipelining: Pipelining is a technique where we arrange the hardware elements in a way that the overall performance is increased. For example: using registers in CPU and doing an operation in ALU to display results back on the register. So, supposing we complete an operation in a total of 6 clock cycles, it would mean that the pipelined machine would enable a 6 times faster execution than the sequential execution with the help of a more effective and 'pipelined' hardware structure. Even though CISC machines are often pipelined too, the RISC computers are made in a way to take advantage of the pipelined architecture. [4]

But using this technique often comes up with pipeline hazards. This occurs when the current instruction tries to fetch the result of the previous uncompleted instruction, most importantly with the branch instructions where the program flow has the option to choose one of the two possible paths. RISC avoids the pipeline hazard by redefining jumping through branches through the delayed branch after every appropriate instruction. It allows redefining the next instruction while performing current instruction. [4]

B. Easier Addressing modes

This advantage helps to make it possible for the operands to have fast address computation. The RISC instructions use register-based addressing, making it faster and easier. The RISC operations break down the complex addressing modes from the simple modes and register-to-register operations allow only LOAD and STORE to access memory and this simplifies handling of hazards, instruction sets, eases the processor, and shortens the cycle time rates. [5]

C. Larger Set of instructions

Not only do they take up extra memory and disk space but also put an extra burden on instruction memory and secondary storage. [4]

D. Simplified instructions

RISC instructions are of fixed length, where the operands and opcode are found at the same position. As they appear in the same location in the encoding of instructions, it allows the decoder to use them immediately without much work. [4]

E. A large number of registers used

As RISC processors employ register-to-register instructions, a large number of registers are put into use which accordingly decreases the overhead on calling and returning functions and operations. [5]

F. The complexity of software increases

As for implementing pipeline, much more complex software would be required. Even though the optimizations used in RISC compilers and compilers for CISC architecture are similar, the only difference is that the ones for RISC are engineered in a way to use the optimizations more ideally. [4]

G. More lines of code, more work for the compiler

As the lines of code are relatively more, more memory (RAM) is required to store the instructions, and also, the compiler does more work to convert the high-level statement to the assembly level.

H. Modern Impact of RISC

The ARM architecture is now the basis for most mobile devices, including smartphones, tablets, and embedded systems. Apple's transition to ARM-based processors in their MacBooks and iPads (e.g., the M1 chip) is a testament to the growing importance of RISC. The key advantage of RISC lies in its ability to execute instructions in fewer cycles, especially through pipelining techniques that are optimized for modern hardware.

III. OVERVIEW OF CISC (COMPLEX INSTRUCTION SET COMPUTER)

CISC architecture was developed to make the task of compiler development simpler and easier. They allow efficient use of memory through their feature of easy programming. The first generation of CISC processors are Intel 80486 and Motorola 68040. Some of the major features, advantages, and drawbacks of using CISC architecture are described below:

A. Transistors used for storing complex instructions

They are relatively larger in size as compared to RISC as they need more transistors to store complex instructions.

B. Emphasis on hardware, small code sizes

The primary approach taken by CISC processors is to complete the operation in a few lines of code as possible and this is made possible by making a processor hardware in a way that it "is capable of understanding and executing a series of operations". [6] More importance is given to make hardware in a way that the complex instructions are built on it. The major advantage of using CISC is that, as the length of the code is very short, the translation of a high-level language statement to assembly level is relatively quick. Due to small code sizes, less memory (RAM) is used to store the instructions. [6]

C. No need to change the ISA every other time, Memory-to-memory instructions

The ease of adding new commands directly onto the chip is possible on CISC which is why we don't need to change the structure of the instruction set every time we want to add new instructions.[6]

D. Less memory usage, better cache performance

Relatively less memory is used as the length of code is short and also, as the program size is smaller too, it improves the cache performance and reduces bus traffic due to less memory requirement for a smaller number of instructions. [3]

E. Modern Impact of CISC

The x86 architecture has evolved significantly over the years, integrating many features once thought to belong to RISC architectures, such as pipelining, superscalar execution, and branch prediction. These improvements have allowed Intel processors to remain competitive with RISC-based systems like ARM in both desktop and server markets.

IV. COMPARISON OF RISC AND CISC

The table below highlights the key differences between RISC and CISC architectures.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF RISC AND CISC PROCESSORS

Feature	RISC	CISC
Instruction Set Complexity	Simple, fewer instructions	Complex, many instructions
Execution Time	Single clock cycle per instruction	Multiple clock cycles per instruction
Memory Usage	More memory due to larger code size	Less memory due to smaller code size
Pipelining Efficiency	Optimized for pipelining	Difficult to pipeline
Hardware Design	Simplified hardware, fewer transistors	Complex hardware, more transistors

V. POTENTIAL CHOICE

Choosing between RISC and CISC rather brings a huge quandary upon us. The development of RISC architectures shifted the emphasis of computer science from hardware to software and companies like Apple started using the RISC architecture. So, better performance depends on characteristics like better architecture, hardware, and software. The following points could help us decipher the exact differences that might help us in giving us a clear answer for this debate:

- The use of branch delay slots provides a huge advantage for RISC as they can implement pipeline in a better way.
- As CISC instructions are written directly to memory, it allows micro-programming and reduces the cost of hard-wiring the control unit as in RISC. This ease of micro-coding allows the engineers to easily increase the compatibility of CISC machines according to the task provided. Even though the instructions used are less in number than RISC, only 20 percent of these instructions are used for the program. [3]
- While converting the CISC code to RISC, known as code expansion, can result in a further increase in the size of RISC instructions. As there's a huge dependency on the compiler, the quality of the code expansion heavily depends on it and the RISC's instruction set. On the other hand, CISC instructions set conditional codes of the instruction which take time to complete and it results in further complexity for the engineer to keep in check the conditional code bits before another instruction edits them. [3]
- The RISC machines fairly have more lines of code as compared to the CISC computer whereas as the name says, 'Complex' Instruction set computer instructions are fairly complex, which operate directly on the computer's memory and don't require any call for storing or loading by the programmer. For small operations like multiplying two numbers on a CISC machine we just write code like:

MULT 1:4, 7:3

While the similar task on RISC will be the following:

LOAD A, 1:4

LOAD B, 7:3

PROD A, B.
STORE 1:4,A [7]

More lines of code would result in more RAM consumption and impose complexity for the compiler. Despite the above disadvantage, RISC surpasses CISC in time complexity like the whole set of instruction implements in one cycle and at the same time as CISC. Similarly, according to its name 'Reduced' ISC, the execution of the program in one cycle makes pipelining possible. Accordingly, fewer transistors are required, allowing the general-purpose registers to come into use. Also, as the tasks get complex, CISC might come up as a complex architecture to operate. Even though the instructions are less in number, the complexity increases.[7]

- The CISC machine reduces its number of instructions to account for having more cycles per instruction. However, RISC does the opposite by sacrificing the number of instructions.
- A large amount of cache imposes another RISC drawback. CISC, having a smaller number of instructions, doesn't increase the cache memory. However, CISC machines use a lot more transistors which correspondingly increases their size.

VI. CONCLUSION

As quoted by Pat Gelsinger in the Microprocessor Debate between him and John Hennessey, *"Over the last five years, the performance gap has been steadily diminishing. It is an unfounded myth that the gap between RISC and CISC, or between x86 and everyone else, is large. It's not large today. Furthermore, it is getting smaller."*

It is hence clear to me how narrow the boundary between both of these architectures is and is almost blurred as both the software and hardware support for CISC and RISC are promptly available to us. The RISC vs CISC debate, once a defining discussion in processor design, has largely blurred in modern computing. While RISC architectures, like ARM, are dominant in mobile and low-power devices due to their efficiency, Intel's x86 processors have incorporated many RISC-like features to improve performance.[9]

The continued evolution of both architectures suggests that their differences are less pronounced today than in the past. Companies like Apple, which transitioned from Intel's CISC-based processors to ARM's RISC-based processors in their M1 chip, highlight the growing convergence of these two models. As hardware and software optimization continues, both RISC and CISC will likely coexist, each serving different needs in the computing landscape.

So, as the world is moving forward with their new concepts and practicing getting rid of the obsolete concept and use the approach which ensures a better future, simplified architectures like RISC are just another step in the development of technology. Hence, keeping in mind the future aspects and the several features and drawbacks discussed, adopting the RISC architecture model not only benefits the processor technology

but also ensures a bright future with more of such significant developments.

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